

CONSTRUCTION PARAMETERS FOR HYPERMEDIA COMICS TO LEARNING BASED ON THE GAMIFICATION CONCEPT

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ABSTRACT

Starting from the construction of a hypermedia comics learning object, this article aims to clarify which gamification elements have been introduced in this artifact. Thus we discuss the relationship between features and elements that make up the games for the student's motivation, the aspects of storytelling games, and the language of comics. Besides the development of the learning objects we emphasize gamification topics used in comics. As a result we identify that many gamification elements contribute in order to make the artifact as emotional as possible. Topics such as fantasy help us to define the theme and genre of comics; clear goals, time and pressure, and feedback help in the dynamic of the students' test. The comics are structured on elements such as: onboarding, levels, challenges, as well as quests and progressive disclosure.

KEYWORDS: *gamification, comics, hypermedia, learning object, experience*

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary reality shows us that we need to adjust learning practices (Lazzarich, 2013), and invest in creative education based on society's current technology (Novaes, 2003). In the learning process it is necessary that teachers invest in extracurricular activities that encourage student participation (Tuncel and Alva, 2010), in order to stimulate student motivation and creativity, which in turn increases student performance, both academically and cognitively (Dias et al., 2004).

In this context we acknowledge the efficacy of storytelling in the learning process (Weller, 2000). However, we understand the development of a learning artifact based on hypermedia storytelling as a challenge, because it is necessary that we explore the nonlinearity possibilities together with characteristics of learning objects (Busarello, 2011).

In a nonlinear environment storytelling unfolds through fragments with connection points between each other, and allows the user to know a story apart from its conventional linearity (Murray, 2003; Steiner and Tomkins, 2010). This immersive aspect enables a more emotional and investigative navigation, facilitating the knowledge assimilation process by the user. It's because this aspects increases the user engage-

ment levels. Moreover, the storytelling in a hypermedia environment favors the three aesthetic categories that amplify user experiences: Immersion, Agency, and Transformation (Murray, 2003).

Based on guidelines of learning object construction (Macedo, 2010) we identified that the learning artifact must have addition to specific content, and must have some way to assess and monitor the student learning process. We emphasize that learning objects should have a clear and measurable goal, and it may be any media on digital or analog formats used for educational purposes. In that sense Busarello (2011) created a hypermedia learning object prototype based on comic language, focusing on learning the graphical representation concepts. This prototype was tested with a volunteer group who approved the effective use of comics for learning. The language of comics was selected because it helps to create an emotional connection with the students (Hughes and King, 2010; Eisner, 2008). Moreover, the structure formed by interconnected images in sequential frames enables greater integration of comics' content and the reader's imagination. It also enabled the readers to impose their individual reading pace, and therefore their personal learning pace (Gerde & Foster, 2008).

We verified, however, that despite hypermedia comics being effective tools for learning (Busarello, 2011), the concept of hypermedia comics covers a huge range of possibilities (McCloud, 2006) that promote the implementation of aesthetic resources (Murray, 2003), which can be deployed in many different ways through a story. We verified that these factors should be further explored alongside the construction of learning objects based on hypermedia comics. One hypothesis is that incorporating gamification concepts in hypermedia comics can contribute to an increase in student motivation through interaction with objects. Within this context, this article's objective is to explain which gamification elements are being introduced to construct learning through hypermedia comics, created by Busarello (2011).

This article is structured as four topics: the first one covers the characteristics and elements that make up the games and its relationship to the individual's motivation. The second topic discusses aspects of the game's storytelling and its relationship with the comic's storytelling. The third one presents the learning object development and the gamification topics and characteristics used by comics. The fourth topic is this article's concluding remarks.

MOTIVATION BY GAMIFICATION

The gamification's concept covers the game engine's uses for problem solving, motivation, and engagement for a given specific audience (Vianna et al., 2013). This approach confirms game thinking by using the systematic and mechanical act of playing in a context outside of the game. It is observed that individuals are motivated to play for four specific reasons: to gain mastery of a particular subject; to relieve stress; as entertainment; and as a means of socialization (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011).

We understand that the difference between the actions within a game and the actions outside the game – the 'diffuse reality of life' – are differentiated by the feelings that individuals have. The first one of which there is a well-defined start and end, where the action rules are conscious and explicit and objects are clear (Collantes, 2013). Thus, the subject defines the actions with reference in the game's final goal. However in actions outside the game we observed that gamification could be applied to activities where it is necessary to stimulate the individual's behavior (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011). The process of learning gamification can contribute to student motivation and the development of cognition (Schmitz et al., 2012).

Based on game mechanics, the concept of motivation is the articulation of an individual's experiences with the proposition of new perspectives 'internal and external of the redefinition processes, from the stimulus to creativity, autonomous thinking and providing welfare to the player' (Vianna et al., 2013, p.30, translation modified). As regards the factors that contribute to the individual's motivation, we identify the intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. The first one

originates within the subject itself (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011). Thus, the individual engages with things willingly because these things awaken interests, challenges, and engage, or give pleasure. The individual motivated in this way will seek news and entertainment, in order to satisfy their curiosity. Moreover, it has the opportunity to develop new skills and learn about something (Vianna et al., 2013). On the other hand, the extrinsic motivation is based on the world surrounding the individual (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). These motivations have as a starting point the subject's desire to obtain an external reward, such as social recognition and material goods (Vianna et al., 2013).

The challenge in creating environments that explore gamification is how to stimulate both forms of motivation in the person. We identify that certain extrinsic rewards can destroy intrinsic motivations that affect the motivational aspect of the individual. In the case of the person's action in an environment, for example, it is of utmost importance that the intrinsic motivations are preserved, otherwise the individual can simply leave this environment (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). The intrinsic behaviors are: 'mechanical'; composed of the elements that enable the game to operate, as well as creating directions for the player's actions; 'dynamics', which are the interactions between player and game mechanics; and 'aesthetics', which determine how the game will make the player feel during the interaction.

Games' characteristics appropriation

The gamification's concept means to appropriate the most effective elements of a game — mechanics, dynamics, and aesthetics — to create and adapt the individual experiences in several fields (Vianna et al., 2013). Once maintained the subject's motivation should provide stimulus to individuals in high-quality and different formats (Li et al., 2012).

Among these stimuli various game elements of mechanics seek to interact with the individual emotionally (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011). The following stand out:

1. Points: enables player monitoring during the interaction with the system. It can both serve as a stimulus for the player, and serve as a parameter so that the developer can read the results of individual performance.
2. Levels: steps that have the intention to indicate the progress of the player within the game.
3. Leaderboard: the purpose is to make simple comparisons, usually through ordered data such as names and scores.
4. Badges: records the goals of steady progress within the system. This topic encourages social promotion.
5. Onboarding: enables an inexperienced player to engage with the system. It indicates the development of player engagement to experience a game for the first time.
6. Challenges and Guests: these challenges for players demonstrate what to do within the game's universe.
7. Engagement loops: emotions that lead the player to re-engage in the experience of the game.
8. Customization: can be characterized in several ways, and enables the processing of system items by the player.

9. Feedback and Reinforcement: generally provide data to the players telling them about the environment and the result of their actions. Resources are essential to the game as a whole.

It is evident that among the characteristic elements of games, those that favor motivation stand out (Li et al., 2012). Fantasy makes for a more exciting experience for the individual, once he or she is embedded in the environment; objects and situations that are not present stimulate the player imagination. Clear goals enable the individual involvement in the system; once he or she objectively understands what must be done. Feedback and guidance enables immediate response by increasing the levels of the individual's engagement. It allows the individual to be conducted in the recovery of an error, if it occurs. Progressive disclosure favors the progressive increase of the user's knowledge while in the game it increases challenge levels. Time and pressure helps to set clear and challenging goals. Rewards allow the subject's performance to be measured by assigning scores after completion of a game level. Stimulus ensures high levels of engagement.

In the developing an artifact based on gamification it is necessary that it presents four essential characteristics (Vianna et al., 2013). The first is the goal of the object, the reason why an individual is performing that activity. It is the purpose designated for such an activity and one that the individual must constantly pursue; it is noted that the concept goes beyond target task completion. The second characteristic is the rules, whose function is to determine how the individual should behave and act towards challenges within a storytelling environment. The rules favor the release of creativity and strategic thinking, once they adjust the level of complexity of individual activities to be performed; the third one is the feedback system, where the individual has guidance about his or her position regarding the factors that regulate the interaction. The fourth is the voluntary participation, which states that the first three topics encourage person participation. We believe that other aspects of games – storytelling, interactivity, graphics support, rewards, competitiveness, virtual environment, among others – are constructed to create a close relationship with the goals, rules, feedback and voluntary participation (Vianna et al., 2013).

STORYTELLING EXPERIENCES: GAMIFICATION X COMICS

We understand that both the act of following a story or playing a game guarantee the individual a storytelling experience. It leads to cognitive experience, which translates into an emotional and sensory product of the individual when engaging in a structured and articulated life. However in the first case, the individual experiences a story where he/she is not included as a character. The individual participates 'live' in the story of another person, but without the possibility of interference in the plot course. In the second case, the individual 'lives' a story. In other words, the storytelling's development

depends on the person's active action for its resolution (Collantes, 2013). This experience feature of the individual in the games becomes an aesthetic category in hypermedia storytelling (Murray, 2003). The understanding is that the possibility found in immersive digital media contributes to building more participatory stories, once the viewer should actively act in the story course. In the case of hypermedia storytelling we identified that the viewer can experience a story in games (Murray, 2003; Brockmeier & Harré, 2003).

In the context of learning, agents present in some games such as character, competition, and game rules may have a direct effect on student development (Schimtz et al., 2012). Similarly, in a story construction these elements can be exploited in various ways. Any linear story covers a character performing actions somewhere, and these actions must respect the rules of the storytelling environment (Field, 2009). It's identified that in the immersion process the user is willing to obey the rules of that new universe, and this involves both aspects of navigation rules such as the story and competition (Murray, 2003).

For the game the storytelling unfolds through a hinged sequentiality of actions that determine the time, and lead to successive transpositions of situations and states (Collantes, 2013). This same characteristic sequential division is perceived in the most basic form of linear storytelling, with the classic division into three acts of a story: presentation, confrontation, and resolution (Field, 2009). The comic's fragmented structure in frames follows a sequential line that plays on the notions of time and space (Cirne, 2000). Also, in comics this sequentiality also allows a nonlinear story view (McCloud, 2006).

Comics are media that are able to create an emotional and physical connection with the reader by virtue of their own formatting in sequential images (Hughes & King, 2010). Used as a learning tool, comics can motivate students (Gerde & Foster, 2008; Iacono & Paula, 2011). Analogously games contribute to the motivation of individuals and therefore present themselves as an alternative in the learning process (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011; Li et al., 2012). The gamification contributes to intensifying the experience of the subject, in order to arouse emotions (Vianna et al., 2013). We identify that one of the main characteristics of this media is the storytelling environment that exploits experiences in stories. These experiences are essential to constitute the memory, communication, and knowledge of individuals (Gordon, 2006).

GAMIFICATION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF HYPERMEDIA COMICS

The learning objects are hypermedia comics that address the Solids concept of the Descriptive Geometry discipline. Basically through solid concepts the students seek to understand the geometric construction of objects represented by three dimensional-space. Based on Busarello (2011) the learning object is storytelling in comics with hypermedia navigation characteristics, with the nonlinear reading possibility be-

tween frame sets. It has links with access to the visualization of data and parallel stories, with the possibility of direct action from the reader, which leads to different story outcomes.

The Descriptive Geometry's contents are inserted as part of the fictional story, while the characters' actions are driven by readers who need the didactic knowledge to be able to interact and read the storytelling. The story theme was based on the humor and adventure genres. All the puzzles involve the solids discipline concept. This choice is based on the fantasy element of the game and seeks to encourage student motivation (Li et al., 2012).

The object's development is based on the proposed construction of learning objects where the nonlinear storytelling identifies that the user should have a single entry and exit of the object, but with several links within it (Nunes et al., 2011). The successful exit of the object is one that passes through the positive answer of the student during the final test. Moreover, the structure allows the user some freedom of choice however guided they are by the environment. Into it the interaction enables the user to feel in control of the story (Craveirinha & Roque, 2010).

As shown in Figure 1 each rectangle corresponds to a comic's page that supports one to three story frames. The arrows show the user's possible navigation. The rectangles in blue, where the description starts with the 'L' letter, represents the links' contents. These provide information about the solids' contents. It is possible to identify that in some parts the story

is divided – as in frames eleven, twelve, and thirteen. At this point the reader is able to follow a specific story character. It allows the reader to view the same subject through different points of view. Moreover it uses the aesthetic category of transformation (Murray, 2003) where the user has the ability to transform him or herself into a specific character. It also uses the Agency where the user action enables the choice of a specific path. In gamification the context of learning agents as character, competition, and game rules may have a direct effect on student development (Schimtz et al., 2012).

The knowledge tests within the object are used to monitor student learning, and are also a means of story navigation. Figure 1 shows that all tests lead to three possible paths. That's because when the test is submitted to the student, he or she should have to choose between three specific issues. If the student's answer is correct he or she is submitted to a story continuation. However if the answer is incorrect the characters are led to situations that induce the student to do the test again. To illustrate this process, the images below show the sequential pages corresponding to the first test's frames, o8, o9, 10.1, 10.2, and 10.3.

Figure 2 presents respectively the frames o8 and o9 (Figure 1). In the plot, the pirates arrive on an island that has a cottage, but while they moor up a sea monster attacks them. To escape, the characters run to enter the cottage. At this moment they need to decipher a puzzle to open the door. The puzzle is a test about a solid concept.

Figure 1. Structure of the Learning object in hypermedia comics

Figure 2. Comic fragments that lead to the test – Frames o8 and o9

Figure 3. Comic fragments in incorrect answer – Frames 10.1 and 10.3

If the student's answer was incorrect, one of the pirates fights the sea monster while the others try opening the door. Figure 3 presents respectively the story frames 10.1 and 10.3 (Figure 1). In the first one the pirate is struggling and those plot frames are the first wrong answer. Thus the student has the chance to do the exercise again. If the students answer the wrong option again, the comic's continuation shows the pirate being captured by the sea monster. These different outcomes are in agreement with other characteristic elements of games (Li et al., 2012):

- Clear Goals: once the student knows he/she has answered the test correctly the story proceeds;
- Time Pressure: once these goals defy the student and the unfolding of the story;
- Feedback: is related to the story continuation after the student answers. In those sequences, if the character is in a laughter situation the students know that the answer is wrong. Conversely, if the answer was correct the story continues its flow.

Figure 4 presents the frame 10.2 (Figure 1) that represents the image next to the correct answer. In it, the characters are safe inside the cottage. This frame does not present a possibility of returning to the test and the student should continue forward.

Figure 4. Comic fragments in correct answer – Frame 10.2

In Figure 1 we can see that the comic's beginning covers more stories and links for learning. It is based on the element of game mechanics onboarding that introduces the student to the storytelling and will also present the rules of the object gradually (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). Similarly the object is composed of five different tests divided into three learning levels, characterized by levels, quests, and challenges, as well as progressive disclosure of the object content (Li et al., 2012). While the students are learning the content, the test becomes more complex. The three comic Levels are: the pirates' journey to the island; the decision of what path each pirate must follow alone; and the final test where they meet up again to find the treasure chest. This distribution regards the division of a linear storytelling (Field, 2009), where the first level is the presentation, the second level the confrontation, and the third the story's resolution.

We believe that the challenges in the plot contribute to increase in individual immersion in the plot (Murray, 2013), as well as student engagement levels (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). Gamification aspects that can be incorporated into learning objects are: experience repetition, different possible paths, recognition and reward (Simões et al., 2013). The first and the second one are identified by the nonlinearity's possibilities into the story. The links associated with the story contents favor the repetition of experience, which is further stressed by tests. Analogously the path possibilities are explicitly identified in the plot parallel stories – between 10.2 and 14 frames – and the nonlinear navigation characteristics. The reward is identified in the continuity of reading at the end of each activity and completion of the story.

Based on the essential features of games (Vianna et al., 2013) the learning object presents a clear goal that is the learning of a solid discipline concept. The actions taken by the student during the storytelling course — story reading, educational content, resolution tests — are goals to be achieved by the individual. The rules are presented through browsing, where the student may choose to see the plot pictures or links and follow the paths of each character. Moreover, the student understands that the answers of tests have a direct effect on the story course. However there are the possibilities of the stu-

dents learning from their mistake and doing the tests again. This topic corroborates the feedback system where the story is used as media to motivate the learning of content. Thus, the feedback of answers leads the student to reading specific continuities in the plot. For example, when an answer is wrong the continuity of reading leads to an unfavorable outcome within history. But if it is correct the story continues. It enables the construction of a single story to each student (Murray, 2003), and consequently affects the learning process. In regards to the voluntary participation, we observed that the use of storytelling comics is a motivating factor in the learning process for students (Gerde & Foster, 2008; Short & Reeves, 2009; Hughes & King, 2010; Busarello, 2011). In the case of our hypermedia comics, the story assists in interpretation and exemplification of content that can seem abstract to students.

FINAL THOUGHTS

This article's objective was to clarify how gamification elements should be introduced in the construction of hypermedia comics for learning. We identified that in storytelling learning, artifact's construction requires the investment in characters and plots that emotionally captivate the student. In regards to the learning object we identified that the descriptive geometry content must be present in the obstacles encountered by the characters, and it should be explored by students during media's nonlinear navigation. The navigation mechanism is tied to the knowledge that the student acquires during reading the story, where the users' shares are parameters for the construction of its own storytelling version. Thus, links enable the student to know more about the learning content or the story. While, the way to assess the student's knowledge must be embedded in the story frames and as part of the plot. A given obstacle that the character must have to overcome is present in this form of test, and it requires the learning student's knowledge. The test's answer feedback determines the story's continuation. The student will know the right or wrong answer depending on the character action in a certain set of frames after the test.

The possibilities in the hypermedia comic's construction favor the concepts of gamification uses, both as student's motivation and for the mechanical's construction of artifact. Construction elements such as fantasy help to define the story theme and genre; clear goals, time and pressure and feedback assist in dynamic assessments that students must do in the course of reading and navigation. The comics are structured based on elements of game mechanics. For example, onboarding, levels, challenges and quests, progressive disclosure, experimentation repetition, and opportunities and reward pathways are used for the characteristic elements of the learning object.

Finally the hypermedia comics learning object presents essential gaming features, such as goals which are linked to learning, rules which structure the way a student interacts with the story and the environment, and system feedback,

which is mainly related to the reviews during reading and the story's sequence after the tests. We believe that these elements may contribute to the student's voluntary participation in the learning.

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